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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF MAGNESIUM SULPHATE AND
NIFEDIPINE IN TOCOLYSIS OF PRETERM LABOUR**¹Dr. Ayesha Khan, ²Dr. Lamia Yusuf, ³Dr. Saba Khalid¹Senior Registrar Rashid Latif Medical College, ²Associate professor Rashid Latif Medical College, ³Senior Registrar Hayat National Hospital, Jazan**Abstract**

Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness and adverse reactions of intravenous magnesium to oral nifedipine for severe tocolysis of preterm labor.

Methods: A multicenter random trial was carried out. Patients specifically in active preterm labor who had been at 24 to 33 weeks and 6 days of pregnancy happened to be at random designated to obtain magnesium sulfate or nifedipine. The elementary results were the arrest of preterm labor, characterized as prevention of delivery for 48 hours with uterine quiescence.

Results: One hundred ninety-two patients had been enlisted. Additional patients designated to magnesium sulfate attained the major result (87% compared with 72%, according to the value of P .01). There had been no distinctions in delivery just in 48 hours (7.6% magnesium sulfate when compared with 8.0% nifedipine, with the value of P .92), gestational age at delivery (35.8 reviewed with 36.0 weeks, P .61), birth earlier 37 and 32 weeks (57% reviewed along with 57%, P .97, and 11% reviewed with 8%, P .39), and episodes of frequent preterm labor. Mild and serious maternal unfavorable effects were considerably more continual with magnesium sulfate. Birth weight, birth weight less than 2,500 g, and neonatal morbidities had been matching in between groups, however, infants in the magnesium sulfate group spent a bit longer in the neonatal intensive care unit (8.8 17.7 in comparison with 4.2 8.2 days, P .007).

Conclusion: Patients that obtained magnesium sulfate obtained the elementary result more frequently. Though, gestational age at delivery, delay of delivery, and neonatal outcomes had been equivalent in between groups. Nifedipine was involved with a lesser number of maternal adverse consequences.

Keywords: Preterm labor; Magnesium sulfate; Nifedipine; Tocolysis; Comparison.

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INTRODUCTION:

Crowther et al. (2014) explained that despite the fact that the preterm birth rate remains to enhance, in the United States of America there are complications (12.3%) of births and making contributions considerably to neonatal mortality and morbidity, deliveries because of PROM (preterm premature rupture of the membranes) and spontaneous preterm birth have actually diminished among the singletons. In between the period of 2000 and 2010 PROM and spontaneous preterm birth both reduced 0.4% among the singletons. The improving level of preterm birth has resulted to some extent through enhancement in preterm delivery for medical symptoms and an enhancement in numerous gestations. Neonatal outcomes have actually enhanced at all gestational age groups because of the portion to antenatal steroid treatment, which usually is facilitated by tocolytic agents and enhancements in neonatal care. The preterm birth cost continues to be substantial, determined to be not less than \$26.2 billion, \$51,600 per preterm infant, in the United States of America in 2010.

Coomarasamy et al. (2016) described that tocolytic agents are applied to hinder uterine contractions and delivery delay. Preferably, tocolytics ought to be reducing maternal incidence even though delaying delivery during the course of antenatal steroids administration. Magnesium sulfate is actually the most frequently utilized the first-line tocolytic in America even though it has recently not been confirmed to generally be exceptional to saline infusion and its actual use happens to be a supply of conflict. Magnesium sulfate involves intravenous administration, has the potentiality for overmedication through severe maternal negative consequence and might be linked with adverse neonatal effects. Whenever reviewed with betamimetics, magnesium sulfate appears to provide a much better maternal protective profile.

Dhawle et al. (2016) claimed that Nifedipine could be most effortlessly endured, is administered orally, and seems to experience limited negative consequence, even though serious dyspnea, hypoxia, and myocardial infarction have now been described with pregnant females, as has fetal death. Whenever reviewed with betamimetics, nifedipine is being involved with a lesser amount of negative responses, sustained pregnancy, and much healthier neonatal consequences. Nifedipine has been reviewed along with magnesium sulfate in two small random types of research. Each research was underpowered, with 80 and 74 patients, correspondingly, and recommended no distinction ineffectiveness or maternal negative

consequence. Nifedipine may hold contractions quicker if compared with magnesium sulfate. Our intention was to evaluate the effectiveness and negative consequence of magnesium sulfate and nifedipine towards the serious tocolysis of preterm labor.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A random clinical test was carried out at two different medical centers.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients in activated preterm labor have been 24 weeks to 33 weeks and 6 days pregnancy were at random allocated to obtain magnesium sulfate or nifedipine. Preterm labor was described by two or a lot more contractions every ten minutes along with cervical modification, ruptured membranes, or two cm or increased dilation and 80% effacement.

Exclusion Criteria

Exemption considerations incorporated placenta previa, placental abruption, non-reassuring fetal status and intrauterine development restriction, chorioamnionitis, and maternal medical disease. Randomization was carried out by sequentially figures opaque envelopes produced from a unique numbers table. All patients obtained beta-methasone, twelve mg intramuscularly twice, twenty-four hours apart, antibiotic prophylaxis advised towards group B Streptococcus, as well as 500 mL hydration along with lactated Ringer's solution prior to tocolysis.

The patients who have preterm premature rupture of membranes additionally received erythromycin. Patients randomly designated to magnesium sulfate obtained a 4-g bolus implemented by 2 g/h infusion. Physicians remained authorized to offer additional 2-g magnesium sulfate boluses as required for constant preterm labor and to enhance the infusion rate up to 4 g/h. Patients designated to nifedipine obtained 10 mg sublingually every 20 minutes for three doses overall, implemented by 20 mg orally every 4 or 6 hours, established on physician assessment. Physicians were advised to carry on treatment with magnesium sulfate or nifedipine until as a minimum of twelve hours of uterine quiescence took place throughout the initial 48 hours. Uterine quiescence was described as 6 or a lesser number of contractions per hour. Following the research procedures were accomplished, physicians were directed to handle patients according to their normal schedule that may or probably won't consist of oral maintenance tocolysis with nifedipine. All patients who are undergone through clinical evaluation for magnesium sulfate toxicity and blood pressure review every fifteen minutes for the first two

hours, and then every four hours throughout the first twenty-four hours of the research. Negative consequences were evaluated by patient consultation from a list of negative consequence and chart comparison.

The elementary research result was avoidance of delivery for 48 hours with the attainment of uterine quiescence, characterized by twelve hours of six or a lesser number of contractions per hour and no additional cervical modification within 48 hours of tocolytic initiation. Failing of the elementary result happened if, in the initial 48 hours, patients directed, ruptured formerly intact membranes, experienced recurrent preterm labor, continual to contract or alter their cervix throughout, or involved the use of auxiliary or different tocolytics. Additional results incorporated hours to quiescence, gestational age at delivery, birth weight, maternal negative consequence, and neonatal morbidities, and a specific length of stay. A serious maternal composite negative consequence incorporated pulmonary edema, chest pain, shortness of breath, and hypotension. All patients who provided to one of the two hospitals in preterm labor and not receiving tocolytic medications have been qualified for research registration. All patients had been listed between

April 26, 2000, and July 11, 2010. Patients were maintained by the participating physicians in combination with resident physicians who had been performing on Labor and Delivery at the time of patient entrance and care.

We anticipated a 35% incidence of failing of the elementary outcome along with magnesium sulfate. To have actually 80% power to detect a 50% decrease in failure, with a two-tailed alpha of 0.05 and a b of 0.2, 192 patients were involved. The specific data were examined by intention to treat, x², Fisher exact test, Student t tests, Wilcoxon rank sum, and Kaplan-Meier survival analysis.

RESULTS:

A total of 196 patients were randomly designated, and 192 patients were listed (Fig. 1). Four patients were omitted after randomization and prior to data research for not fulfilling study entry requirements. One patient's office chart unveiled that she was at 35 weeks of gestation; she had not yet accepted tocolysis. Three patients did not match criteria for preterm labor: two had cervical dilation but no contractions and one had constant uterine contractions but no cervical alteration.

Figure 01 (Flow Diagram of Randomization)

Ninety-two patients received magnesium sulfate, and 100 patients received nifedipine. Our patient population is described in Table 1.

Characteristics	Magnesium Sulfate (n 92)	Nifedipine (n 100)	P
Age	26.6 6.8	26.3 6.3	.38
Age 35 y or older	1	1	
	4 (15)	1 (11)	.39
Public assistance	6	6	
	4 (69)	8 (68)	.82
Multiparous	4	5	
	1 (45)	5 (55)	.15
Prior preterm birth	1	1	
	2 (13)	9 (19)	.26
Gestational age at enrollment (wk)	30.8 2.3	31.2 2.1	.92
Dilation at start of tocolysis (cm)	1.9 0.98	1.8 0.93	.30
Effacement at start (cm)	2.2 1.1	2.2 1.2	.65
Contraction frequency at start (min)	3.6 1.5	3.5 1.2	.24
	2	1	
Twins	0 (22)	7 (17)	.40
Preterm PROM	4(4)	4(4)	.90
	3	4	
Maintenance tocolysis	3 (38)	2 (42)	.57

(Source:Dhawle et al., 2016)

Generally there were definitely no distinctions in between the groups with aspect to patient demographics and obstetric attributes, (Table 1) nor had been there variations in between the 2 research centers in type of medication provided, complete medications provided at 24 and 48 hours, failing of the elementary consequence, failing time and uterine quiescence time. At 24 and 48 hours the mean total medication of patient accepted had been 52.4 g and 79.8 g in the group of magnesium sulfate and in the group of nifedipine it was 84.6 mg and 136.3 mg. Generally, there had been no variations between groups in regards to the number who obtained maintenance tocolysis with nifedipine. Considerably increased patients designated to obtain magnesium

sulfate attained the elementary results of prevention of preterm delivery for 48 hours with uterine quiescence (according to the comparison of 87% with 72%, P .01, as mentioned in below Table 2) and this particular retained accurate when we ruled out from evaluation patients along with twins and preterm PROM. Nevertheless, involving all patients who actually attained the elementary outcome, uterine quiescence time was quicker with nifedipine. There have been no variations in between the groups in the ratio of patients who actually delivered within 48 hours, delivery before 37 and 32 weeks and gestational age at delivery, or episodes of recurrent preterm labor.

Table 2 - Magnesium Sulfate Compared With Nifedipine, Outcomes

	Magnesium Sulfate (n 92)	Nifedipine (n 100)	P
Primary outcome	80(87)	72(72)	.01
Primary outcome excluding preterm PROM	76(86)	70(73)	.02
Primary outcome excluding twins	62(86)	61(73)	.05
Time to quiescence (h)	8.4 6.5	6.1 6.3	.02
Delivery in 48 hours	7(7.6)	8(8.0)	.92
Gestational age at delivery (wk)	35.8 3.4	36.0 3.1	.61
Gestational age less than 37 wk	50(57)	52(57)	.97
Gestational age less than 32 wk	10(11)	7(8)	.39
Episodes recurrent preterm labor	0.44 .61	0.40 .61	.32

PROM, premature rupture of membranes - Data are n (%) or mean

Standard Deviation

(Source: Dhawle et al., 2016)

DISCUSSION:

Established on our query of the English Language Literature at PubMed from 2000 to 2010, while utilizing the basic combination of keywords “magnesium sulfate,” “nifedipine,” “preterm labor,” and “tocolysis,” this particular is the biggest random research evaluating magnesium sulfate and nifedipine.

According to this research, magnesium sulfate attained the elementary result more often as compared with nifedipine. Nonetheless, no distinctions had been recognized in between drugs in gestational age at delivery or major neonatal outcomes and delay of delivery. Nifedipine was involved with considerably a lesser amount of slight and significant maternal negative consequence (Kamat, Veena and Rani, 2016).

Illustrated by Lyell and El-Sayed(2016) magnesium sulfate has recently been a lot of regularly utilized tocolytic at both study sites. Eleven nifedipine patients had been altered to magnesium sulfate due to the fact of chronic uterine contractions alone, lacking clearly recorded proof of cervical change, an obvious infraction of the study process. No women treated with magnesium sulfate were modified to nifedipine. All eleven patients had been regarded to have failed the elementary results and had been examined by intent to treat. Regretfully, we do not have proper information about what would definitely have occurred had these types of acquiring patients continued on nifedipine for the full 48-hour window, exactly how many would have attained the elementary outcome, and even if nifedipine would certainly have attained uterine quiescence more quickly than magnesium sulfate.

According to the descriptions of McNamara, Crowther and Brown (2015)the fact of the practice

positions at both discussed hospitals where magnesium sulfate has typically been the first line tocolytic of preference, we predicted and pursued to decrease this research bias by utilizing uterine quiescence as part of the elementary result; patients who obtained magnesium sulfate but carried on to contract all through the 48-hour window was not able to be considered as effective. Significantly, irrespective of which tocolytic the patient received, birth weight, gestational age at delivery, and significant neonatal morbidities were not separate between groups. This research recommends that someone can smartly begin nifedipine, and transform the patient to another tocolytic if needed.

Several researchers have raised safety issues along with oral and sublingual nifedipine in pregnant and non-pregnant patients. Nifedipine antagonizes voltage based L-type calcium channels, triggering vascular and smooth muscle relaxation, reflexive cardioacceleration, vasodilatation, and improved sympathetic tone. Whenever applied during the course of the hypertensive crisis, nifedipine can contribute to severe hypotension resultant in cerebrovascular ischemia, stroke, fetal distress, myocardial infarction, conduction disturbances, as well as death. The instant discharge formulation can decline blood pressure within 5 to 10 minutes. Whenever applied for tocolysis, diastolic blood pressure has been revealed to decline by 8% after the initial sublingual dose, heart rate also improves, and the influence lasts for 3 hours. Twenty minutes after oral, as in contrast to sublingual, dosing, diastolic blood pressure diminished by a mean of 11%, and heart rate enhanced. Nifedipine half-life was 1.35 hours. For the reason that of the potential for hypotension we pre-hydrated all the patients with 500 mL of lactated Ringer’s solution, supervised blood pressure regularly, and excluded females with hypertension or cardiac disease.

Table 3

	Magnesium Sulfate (n 92)	Nifedipine (n 100)	P
Any adverse effects	60(65)	34(34)	.001
Serious adverse effects*	20(22)	10(10)	.03
Shortness of breath	13(14)	5(5)	.03
Pulmonary edema	3(3)	0(0)	.07
Hypotension	2(3)	3(5)	.72
Chest pain	7(8)	4(4)	.28
Lethargy	27(29)	3(3)	.001
Nausea	29(32)	6(6)	.001
Vomiting	24(26)	5(5)	.001
Flushing	20(22)	1(1)	.001
Blurry vision	12(13)	0(0)	.001
Dizziness	16(17)	3(3)	.001
Double vision	3(3.3)	0(0)	.07
Headache	11(12)	22(24)	.07
Palpitations	1(1)	0(0)	.30
Heartburn	6(7)	6(6)	.87

Data are n (%).

Table 4

	Magnesium Sulfate (n 106)	Nifedipine (n 110)	P
Birth weight (g)	2,550 802	2,650 698	.38
Birth weight less than 2,500 g	52(49)	46(42)	.48
RDS	24(23)	21(19)	.48
IVH	3(3)	2(2)	.61
NEC	0	0	
Sepsis	5(5)	3(3)	.43
Death	1(1)	0	.31
Composite morbidity [†]	27(25)	22(20)	.32
NICU admission	55(52)	41(37)	.04
GA at NICU admission (wk)	33.1 2.3	33.8 2.2	.28
BW at NICU admission (g)	1,973 494	2,095 570	.38
Days in NICU	8.8 17.7	4.2 8.2	.007

Maternal negative consequence happened in almost two-thirds of females revealed to magnesium sulfate and one-third of females revealed to nifedipine, a considerable and important variation. Of interest, severe negative consequence, incorporating shortness of breath and pulmonary edema, had been also more consistent along with magnesium sulfate. Important hypotension was basically not observed among the nifedipine patients, even though Glock and Morales identify transient hypotension, enduring less than 10 minutes and not involving drug discontinuance, among 41% of nifedipine patients. Eliminating blood pressure variations, they revealed more negative

consequence among the magnesium sulfate patients, 10% of whom expected drug discontinuance (Rani Balasubramani and Kamatchi, 2017).

No variation in any of the leading neonatal results was mentioned in between groups. We specifically did discover that newborns revealed to magnesium sulfate spent additional duration in the NICU in spite of an equivalent incidence of leading morbidities and equivalent birth weights and gestational ages at delivery and at NICU admission. This presented data do not provide a transparent description of these discoveries. Subsequently, our research could not

deal with the frequently numerous and complicated variety of causes for NICU admission and constant hospitalization. No matter if there is an occasional connection in between magnesium sulfate and NICU length of stay is unverified and merits upcoming research(Stevenson, 2016).

Some researchers have believed that magnesium sulfate may slow down gastrointestinal function, directing to feeding issues, and may contribute to immense respiratory suppression. As we also compare the two previous research evaluating magnesium sulfate with nifedipine, NICU length of stay was not evaluated in one and was revealed as not separate in the other, but the patient's number involved was not given. Neonatal ICU (intensive care unit) stay was not sustained when magnesium sulfate was reviewed with saline infusion. A few have indicated considerations regarding fetal exposure to tocolytic doses of magnesium sulfate A Cochrane meta-analysis recommended enhanced fetal and pediatric death associated to magnesium sulfate exposure (relative risk 2.82, with 95% confidence interval 1.2– 6.62), even though all fatalities were from only one of the several studies under comparison.

Some other studies have actually revealed that magnesium sulfate exposure does not boost neonatal mortality or morbidity and in fact, it might protect against gross motor dysfunction. In Glock and Morales' experiment of magnesium sulfate compared with nifedipine, there were two neonatal deaths, both assigned to overwhelming prematurity, and both from the nifedipine group.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

This research was limited by multiple aspects. Neither magnesium sulfate nor nifedipine has been revealed to be an excellent tocolytic in a double-blind, placebo-controlled experiment. Nevertheless, tocolytic agents were already revealed to delay delivery for 48 hours, with the supposed benefit of permitting steroid administration or maternal transport. While performing the specific placebo-controlled, experiment of tocolysis in the time period of the window of steroid treatment is external from care standard of our societies. Double-Blind research evaluating magnesium sulfate and nifedipine would benefit from overcome potential physician administration bias according to this research, while maternal negative consequences might make difficult. Fetal fibronectin was not a requirement for study entry because it was not initially available at both study sites. Ideally, a study of preterm labor would exclude patients with unfavorable fetal

fibronectin. We registered patients, though, who were clinically in active preterm labor. Despite the fact that the optimal doses of magnesium sulfate and nifedipine have not been demonstrated, we applied the standard doses utilized according to our institutions. Though, larger doses may be required for clinical effectiveness. Our nifedipine protocol has been examined among patients in the premises of our institution, with maximum efficacy and safety evidence.

CONCLUSION:

In the concluding note, magnesium sulfate attained the elementary results (prevention of delivery for 48 hours with uterine quiescence) more often as compared with nifedipine. Though, no differences have been recognized between drugs in delivery delay and gestational age at delivery along-with major neonatal outcomes. Nifedipine was related with considerably less mild and serious maternal negative consequence.

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